

THE EMERGENCE OF RESPECTABLE RELIGIONS

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Annotation. In our religion, sect is the basis that every Muslim should pay attention to. Because a person achieves his goal by means of the path created by sects. That is why sect has great importance in religion. This thesis briefly discusses the emergence of respected sects in Islam.

Key words: Kufa, Basra, Mecca, Medina, fiqh, jurist, fuqaha, mujtahid, ijtihaad.

With the passage of time, with the demands of the times, the science of Islamic jurisprudence, that is, the science of jurisprudence, developed and gradually separated from tafsir and hadith and other Islamic sciences. After the death of the Prophet, may the peace and blessings of God be upon him, the period of the Companions and then the period of the followers was decided. In the first decades of the second Hijri century, the first jurisprudential sects began to emerge. The methods and rules used by these sects were not systematized and did not take any official form. The jurists of this sect were talented people in their fields and were interested in all the sciences, issues, exegesis, hadith and jurisprudence based on the teachings of Islam, and had extensive knowledge and high skills in them. were Based on their personal interests, they rose among the Muslim community and earned the trust and respect of all people with their knowledge and qualities..

The first jurisprudential schools belonging to Ahl al-Sunnah wal-Jamaa are as follows:

1. Madhhab of jurists
2. Makka of jurists
3. Basra of jurists
4. Ko'fa of jurists
5. Shom of jurists

The jurisprudence of Basra and Kufa constitute the jurisprudence of Iraq. The famous representatives of the first jurisprudential schools are as follows:

1. The representatives of Madinah jurisprudence: Umar ibn Khattab, Ali ibn Abu Talib, Abdullah ibn Umar, Zayd ibn Thabit, Said ibn Musayyib, Zuhri, Yahya ibn Said, and others..

2. Proponents of the Meccan school of jurisprudence: Abdullah ibn Abbas, Sufyan ibn Uyaina, Muslim ibn Khalid.

3. Representatives of the Iraqi school of jurisprudence: Abdullah ibn Mas'ud, Alqama ibn Qais, Qazi Shurayh, Ibrahim Nakha'i, Hammad ibn Sulaiman, Ibn Abu Laila.

4. Abdurrahman Avzai, the founder of his sect, was the representative of the Sham fiqh school..

According to experts in the history of jurisprudence, among these madhhabs, the Iraqi jurisprudential madhhab was the center with a special place. The most important aspects of the early jurisprudential schools were that they were based on the Qur'an and paid great attention to the Sunnah. At that time, qiyas as the main source of Shari'ah did not go through the development period, so they did not use this method on a large scale. With the passage of time, the religion of Islam spread on a large scale and people belonging to different religions accepted Islam due to some political, social and ideological reasons. and this phenomenon made it difficult to use this source with strict confidence. As a result, by this time, there was a need to analyze hadiths in depth, to exclude fake hadiths from among them, and to use only authentic hadiths, i.e., hadiths narrated from the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, as jurisprudential sources. Such an approach, on the one hand, led to the development of the science of hadith studies, and on the other hand, it created the ground for the emergence of new jurisprudential schools..

A critical approach to the working method of the first legal sects, scholars who were supporters of the new method appeared in each sect. Thus, on the basis of the first jurisprudential sects, four main jurisprudential sects were formed, each of which belonged to the Sunna wal community, and each of them developed according to the conditions of their environment. In this regard, the fiqh of the people of Sunnah wa al-Jamaa has gone through its stages of development as a perfect and developed fiqh system. In the II-III centuries of Hijri (722-922), in the fields where these jurisprudence schools emerged, great jurists and eminent mujtahids matured. Since they contributed their fair share to the development of various jurisprudence schools, this period in the history of Islamic jurisprudence was called the "golden period". During this period, a great series of great jurists fulfilled their duties. Each of the Sunni sects founded and developed by the great mujtahids was named after its founder. They consist of the following:

1. On the basis of the first jurisprudential school of Iraq, which was the union of Kufa and Basra, the "Hanafi" school was founded by Abu Hanifa..

2. On the basis of the first jurisprudential school of Madinah, the "Maliki" school was established by Imam Malik.

3. Even though Imam Shafi'i started his madhhab "Shafi'i" as a manifestation of the Madinah madhhab, he combined the teachings of Ahl al-Hadith and Ahl al-Ray' with a lot of use of the Hanafi madhhab, after he went to Egypt. founded z sects.

4. The "Hanbali" madhhab was founded by Imam Ahmat ibn Hanbal on the basis of the first jurisprudential madhhab of Mecca..

Conclusion. It resolves each legal sect of the Sunni sects in its own way. Each of these sects, which arose in different places, differ from each other in the way they develop under the influence of specific socio-economic conditions, use the main sources and refer to local customs. During this period, Abdurrahman Avza'i, Davud Zahiri and Ibn Jarir Tobarri also founded three madhhabs belonging to the "people of the Sunnah and community". Some of them began to spread to different regions. But even though their knowledge was sometimes developed on a scientific basis, under the influence of a number of factors, it did not have the opportunity to penetrate among the people on a large scale, and gradually gave its place to the schools of Hanafi, Maliki and Shafi'i. released and left the field of action. In the end, the four schools of jurisprudence, Hanafi, Maliki, Shafi'i, and Hanbali, which retained their status, are still gaining popularity in the Islamic world and satisfying the needs of Muslims.

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